

Mutual Exclusivity in Classical Probability and Related Information in Entangled States Part 2

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In Part 1, we suggested that quantum mechanics involves entangled states which may contain information about classical probabilities. We focused on the 2-slit experiment and argued that if slit widths/separations are of the order of \hbar/p , a photon/particle interacts with both slits creating an entangled state. The classical probability of passing through one slit or the other, however, exists at the same time and the argument was that one should be able to find this value from the entangled state. This involves writing the entangled state as $F_1(x,y)+F_2(x,y)$ (1 for slit 1, 2 for slit) with F_1, F_2 being both positive and negative and somehow related to probability. The positivity/negativity was enforced to ensure a physical state and not a classical OR sum of probabilities. (For example, .5 heads+.5 tails is not a physical state.) To obtain a positive probability, one is forced to square F_1+F_2 and to ultimately obtain the probability to pass through one slit or the other, integrate over dx, dy . This requires that F_1 and F_2 be orthogonal.

Here we consider the classical spatial probability of a particle with constant momentum and velocity a priori, namely $P(x)dx=dx/O$. This is equivalent to conservation of momentum. In this scenario, one has the reverse situation of the 2 slit experiment. One knows the classical probability and wishes to find information about a quantum description (like F_1 or F_2). This suggests one should have two orthogonal or mutually exclusive states, but there is only one momentum linked with $1/L$, i.e. no set of two naturally exclusive states. There is, however, a set of all different p values which have the same probability p . One may thus create a two set state by choosing any p_1 and p_2 which differ. This then leads to $F_1(x) + F_2(x)$ where now 1 refers to p_1 and 2 to p_2 . This is better written as $F(p_1,x)+F(p_2,x)$. Squaring and integrating of dx (according to the rule of Part 1) implies that $\int F(p_1,x)F(p_1,x) dx = 1$ and the same for $F(p_2,x)$ and that $\int F(p_1,x)F(p_2,x) dx = 0$. As a result, $F(p_1,x)$ and $F(p_2,x)$ must be orthogonal functions and $\int F(p,x)F(p,x) dx=1$. It is not clear over what range dx lies and so if one enforces $F(p,x)F(p,x)=1$, then one has $F(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$ as a possible solution. In such a case, one must use $\int F^*(p,x)F(p,x)dx / \int dx = 1$ and $\int F^*(p_2,x)F(p_1,x)dx=0$. This suggests that given a classical probability of 1 for space, one knows that there is an associated p , but $-p$ is just as good and one cannot separate out the two from $P(x)dx=dx$. Thus, we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the formalism introduced in Part I to describe a 2-slit experiment. We note that in Part I, we did not directly derive $\exp(ipx)$.

We belabour the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ because in (1) it suggested almost a priori that an $F(p,x)$ exists and that $\int dx F^*(p_1,x)F(p_2,x) = \delta(p_1,p_2)$. This approach is mathematically identical to arguing for a kind of probability which enforces conservation of momentum (as we have argued in a previous note), but that it seems that more general ideas may be present such as those discussed in Part I.

Mutual Exclusive Classical Probability and Orthogonal States

We argued in Part I that the 2-slit experiment demonstrates the existence of a physical entangled state in nature for photons/particles. In particular, classical mechanics treats a particle as a point both in terms of trajectory and interaction. We suggest that in the 2-slit experiment, the particle is a point in terms of trajectory, but not in terms of interaction if \hbar/p is of the order to the slit widths/separations. In such a case, the particle/photon passes through one slit or the other, but interacts with both, creating an entangled state. There is a probability to pass through one slit or the other (.5 if the slits are the same), but we argued in Part I that this should follow from a description of the entangled state. Given that an entangled state is linked to slit 1 and slit 2, we wrote:

$$F_1(x,y) + F_2(x,y) \quad ((1))$$

F_1 and F_2 must be both positive and negative because an entangled state is physical and not an OR sum of probabilities. To obtain a probability, one must square F_1+F_2 (according to Part I). This yields a distribution or intensity probability for photons/particles, but integrating over $dx dy$ yields the probability for the particle/photon to pass through one slit or the other. This means that:

$$\int dx dy F_1(x,y)F_2(x,y)=0 \quad ((2))$$

Thus, there exist functions F_1, F_2 (called wavefunctions in quantum mechanics). These may be added like usual OR scenarios in probability, but classical probability is obtained by squaring and then integrating and so F_1 and F_2 associated with mutually exclusive classical measurements must be orthogonal functions.

The Case of a Free Particle

The classical spatial probability for a free particle is:

$$P(x)dx = 1/L dx \quad \text{where } L \text{ is an arbitrary length} \quad ((3))$$

According to the ideas of Part I, ((3)) should be the square of an F_1+F_2 such that F_1 and F_2 are orthogonal. This seems to pose a problem as $1/L$ holds for any constant p or velocity. One does not have two particular options or mutually exclusive events (like slit 1, slit 2 in the 2-slit apparatus). We argue, however, that $1/L$ holds for any p_1, p_2 . There is an infinite set of momentum values and one may choose any two. The mutual exclusivity of these is equivalent to conservation of momentum because $1/L$ depends entirely on conservation of momentum, although it is seldom expressed in this manner in the literature, it seems. According to the formalism of Part 1, one should be able to write:

$$F_1(x) + F_2(x) \quad \text{where } 1 \text{ refers to } p_1 \text{ and } 2, \text{ to } p_2 \quad ((4))$$

F_1+F_2 should be squared and integrated such that:

$$\int dx F_1 F_2 = 1, \quad \int F_2 F_2 dx = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \int F_1 F_2 dx = 0 \quad ((5))$$

The integral length is L which is completely arbitrary. One should then, it seems insist that:

$$F_1 = F(p_1, x) \text{ :yield } F(p_1, x)F(p_1, x) = 1 \quad ((6))$$

In this situation, there is no arbitrary length L. A solution of ((5)) then becomes:

$$F(p, x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is the free particle quantum wavefunction and has physical implications in that it creates a diffraction/interference pattern for a 2-slit apparatus with widths/separations of the order of \hbar/p . (This requires writing $F^*(p_1, x)F(p_2, x) = 0$ for $p_1 \neq p_2$.)

In other words, the free particle $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the 2-slit formalism discussed in Part I.

The Work of (1)

In (1) it is suggested that one may obtain photon quantum mechanics directly from the dynamical statement:

$$E = \sqrt{p \cdot p} \quad ((8))$$

A function is introduced such that: $E W = H W$ ((9)) where H represents $\sqrt{p \cdot p}$. The bottom line seems to be that $W(p, x)$ should satisfy:

$$\int dx W^*(p_1, x)W(p_2, x) = \delta(p_1, p_2) \quad ((9))$$

We argue that this is essentially an argument for a kind of probability $W(p, x)$ which ensures conservation of momentum, although it is not directly stated in such a manner in (1). We also suggest that it is somewhat abrupt to introduce probability (and even a square root probability $W(x)$) in such a manner as there is usually no probability in dynamics, i.e. in $E=pc$ a priori. We suggest that the formalism of Part I seems to more naturally introduce these ideas in that one has an entangled state which should yield probabilities of passing through one slit or the other slit. This probability physically exists and so one may mathematically postulate a description of an entangled state which yields such a probability. This means that the description of the entangled state itself must somehow be linked to probability, on the one hand, but must describe a physical state (the entangled state) and not a classical OR sum of probabilities. Thus, we argued in Part I that one does not have $F_1(x, y) + F_2(x, y)$ (1 = slit 1, 2 = slit 2) with F_1 and F_2 positive everywhere.

P versus -P

In the above arguments, $\exp(ipx)$ arose because one required that $\int dx \exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \delta(p_1,p_2)$. This means that $1 = \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. In other words, given the classical $P(x)=\text{constant}$ one knows that physically this applies to a given p , but one cannot really separate p from $-p$. In other words, p and $-p$, even though different, are closely linked while p_1 and p_2 (with $p_1 \neq p_2$ and $\neq -p_1$) are not.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we take a formalism present in Part I and apply it in reverse to a classical spatial probability: $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length. The formalism of Part I involves two mutually exclusive events (passing through slit 1 or slit 2 in a 2-slit experiment). One then writes $F_1(x,y)+F_2(x,y)$ with F_1, F_2 being both positive and negative and somehow linked to probability. The positivity/negativity is needed to create a physical state and not simply a classical OR sum of probabilities. F_1+F_2 is then squared and integrated over $dx dy$ so $\int dx dy F_1 F_2 = 0$.

In the case of $P(x)=1/L$, one might argue that there is only one p or velocity, i.e. $1/L$ holds for all p , e.g. p_1, p_2, p_3 etc. One may choose any two and write $F_1(x)+F_2(x)$. Here 1 applies to p_1 and 2, to p_2 . Then: $\int dx F(p_1,x)F(p_1,x)=1$, but this integral would be over L , an arbitrary length. To remove this arbitrariness, one may impose $F(p_1,x)F(p_1,x)=1$, instead. The second requirement is: $\int dx F(p_1,x)F(p_2,x)=0$. A solution is $F=\exp(ipx)$ with $F^*(px)F(px)=1$ and $\int dx F^*(px)F(p_2x)=0$ for $p \neq p_2$. This is equivalent to conservation of momentum, as we have argued in a previous note.

We argue that the notions of a free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, follow from the formalism developed for describing a 2-slit entangled state which gives rise to the classical probabilities for a photon/particle passing through one slit or the other.

References

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